

**Condensation of Amidines with Ethoxy-
methylene Derivatives of β -Ketonic
Esters, β -Diketones and
Cyanacetic Ester.**

Part II.

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It has been shown by one of us that benzamidine and *p*-toluamidine condense readily with ethylethoxymethylene acetoacetate and ethylethoxymethylene malonate giving rise to pyrimidine derivatives (Mitter and Bardhan, J. Chem. Soc., 1923, 123, 2179). This work has now been extended, on the one hand by using aliphatic amidines like acetamidine and guanidine and on the other hand by taking more complex amidines like anisamidine and naphthamidine. With the exception of acetamidine which apparently decomposes in course of the reaction, the expected pyrimidines have been obtained in every case.

We have also studied the condensation of amidines with ethylethoxymethylene cyanacetate as it was expected that the presence of the additional reactive centre—the cyanogen group—will make its presence felt by giving rise to other sets of condensation products. Our expectations in this respect have been fully realised and we have in the majority of the cases investigated, got

at least one product—in some cases even two—in addition to the expected cyano-pyrimidine. The constitution of these substances is still under investigation and will form the subject-matter of a later communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Pyrimidines from Ethyl Ethoxymethylenecyanacetate.*

Condensation with Benzamidine: Formation of 4-Keto-5-cyano-2-phenyl-1:4-dihydropyrimidine.

The reaction was brought about by treating benzamidine hydrochloride (2.4 gms.) suspended in slightly more than the calculated amount of sodium ethoxide solution, with ethyl ethoxymethylenecyanacetate (2.2 gms.) and digesting the mixture for about an hour. The alcohol was then removed by evaporation, the residue dissolved in water and the liquid acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The condensation product separated as a thick white deposit which when dry weighed 3 gms. Glacial acetic acid was found to be the only solvent that dissolved it completely and from this solution a very poor yield of fine glistening needles were obtained melting at 295° C.

(Found: N=21.52. $C_{11}H_7ON_3$ requires N=21.3 per cent.)

From the mother-liquor was obtained two substances, one melting between 145°–52° and the other at 130°, the constitutions of which have not yet been definitely ascertained.

The hydrolysis of the cyano-compound described above was effected by treating it with an excess of sulphuric

acid diluted with molecular proportion of water (*i.e.*, with $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$). The substance dissolved in the acid freely in the cold. The solution was boiled under reflux for an hour. On cooling and diluting with water the product separated which crystallized from dil. acetic acid in short elongated rectangles melting with effervescence to a clear liquid at 271°C .

(Found: $\text{N}=12.68$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires $\text{N}=12.96$ per cent.)

Condensation with p-Toluamidine: Formation of 4-Keto-5-cyano-2-tolyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine.

The condensation product separated from glacial acetic acid in white flaky plate-like crystals. It melts at $303^\circ\text{-}4^\circ\text{C}$ to a clear colourless liquid and like other cyanopyrimidines, it is insoluble in all other common organic solvents. (Found: $\text{N}=20.08$. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_3$ requires $\text{N}=19.9$ per cent.) Besides the above another impure product was obtained from the mother-liquor.

The hydrolysis product crystallized from dilute acetic acid in prismatic needles melting at 282°C . The substance was found to be identical with the compound obtained by hydrolysing the ester from toluamidine and ethyl-ethoxymethylenemalonate. (Mitter and Bardhan J. Chem. Soc., 123, 2179).

Condensation with p-Anisamidine: Formation of 4-Keto-5-cyano-2-anisyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine.

The substance was obtained from glacial acetic acid as a greenish white crystalline powder melting at 286°C .

(Found: $\text{N}=18.54$. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires $\text{N}=18.50$ per cent.)

The carboxylic acid was obtained by hydrolysis of the above in the form of meshes of very fine needles and

crystallized from a large excess boiling alcohol in stars of concentric needles, which melted at 271°C. with effervescence. The substance is sparingly soluble in the common solvents. The same acid has been obtained by hydrolysing the ester formed from anisamidine and ethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate.

(Found: N=11.59. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N=11.88 per cent.)

Condensation of β -Naphthamidine: Formation of 4-Keto-5-cyano-2- β -naphthyl-1:4-dihydropyrimidine.

The yellow condensation product was crystallized from glacial acetic acid with the addition of animal charcoal. On cooling long slender hair-like yellow needles were obtained which melted sharply to a yellow liquid at 305°-6° C

(Found: N=16.83. $C_{15}H_9ON_3$ requires N=17.0 per cent.)

The hydrolysis product of the above is scarcely soluble in any of the common organic solvents. It dissolves in a very large excess of glacial acetic acid. Hence it was purified only by repeated precipitation from alkali solution by dilute hydrochloric acid. It melts with effervescence at 291°C

(Found: N=10.65. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N=10.52 per cent.)

From the mother-liquor was obtained a substance melting at 147°-148° which is still under investigation.

(b) *Pyrimidines from Ethyl Ethoxymethyleneacetate.*

Condensation with Guanidine: Formation of Ethyl-4-methyl-2-aminopyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

Sodium (0.35 gms.) was dissolved in alcohol and the solution well-cooled by immersion in ice water.

Guanidine carbonate (2.2 gms.) was then added when the free amidine was liberated. To this was introduced the ethyl ethoxymethyleneacetoacetate slowly drop by drop with constant stirring. The whole mass solidified almost instantaneously and the last drops of the ethoxymethylene compound gave a rose red coloration. After standing in ice for more than a quarter of an hour more alcohol was added, and half of the mixture taken in a separate flask and gently boiled over water-bath for an hour, while the other half was left undisturbed in the cooling bath. The two products, obtained under these two different conditions were however found to be the same. These were filtered, washed well with water and crystallized from alcohol in short thin needles thickly interwoven into a mesh. It could also be very easily crystallized from acetone. It melted at 222°C.

(Found: N=23.6. $C_8H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N=23.2 per cent.)

The hydrolysis of the ester was effected by heating it with alcoholic potassium hydroxide under reflux. The alcohol was then evaporated off, the residue dissolved in water, filtered and just acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, excess being avoided since the amido acid is soluble in mineral acids. The precipitate was washed with water and purified by repeated precipitation from its solution in alkali by dilute mineral acid. The substance melts at 256-8°C with decomposition.

(Found: N=27.79. $C_8H_7O_2N_3$ requires N=27.45 per cent.)

Condensation with Anisamidine: Formation of Ethyl 2-anisyl-4-methylpyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

The action of anisamidine on ethylethoxymethyleneacetoacetate takes place readily when solutions of sodium

(1 atom) and the hydrochloride of the base (1 mol.) in alcohol are mixed, the ethoxymethylene derivative (1 mol.) cautiously added and the mixture heated on the water-bath in the usual manner. No deep coloration or setting to a solid could be observed. On cooling a part only separated. The liquid was allowed to stand after the addition of a little water, when clusters of crystalline needles were obtained. The substance was very soluble in alcohol. It melted to a clear liquid at 80°C.

(Found: N=10·8. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N=10·3 per cent.)

The corresponding acid was obtained without much difficulty when the ester was boiled with alcoholic potash for four hours under reflux. The acid crystallized from methyl alcohol in short silky needles melting at 232-3°C.

(Found: N=11·6. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N=10·9 per cent.)

Condensation with Naphthamidine: Formation of Ethyl-2-β-naphthyl-4-methylpyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

This consideration takes place with the utmost ease when the usual procedure is adopted. On the addition of ethyl ethoxymethyleneacetate to the liberated amidine, the whole set to a solid mass. The mixture was then boiled for 40 minutes. On cooling clusters of concentric needles were obtained, which could be very easily crystallized from alcohol. The substance melts at 118°C.

(Found: N=9·77. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N=9·58 per cent.)

The ester was hydrolysed as usual by digestion with alcoholic potash for four hours, the potassium salt being obtained by distilling off the alcohol. It was dissolved in water, filtered from the suspended impurities and acidified by dilute mineral acid when a voluminous

gelatinous ppt. was obtained which crystallized from alcohol and melted at 245-46°C.

(Found: N=10.8. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N_2$, requires N=10.6 per cent.)

(c) *Pyrimidines from Ethoxymethyleneacetylacetone.*

Condensation with Anisamidine: Formation of 5-Acetyl-2-anisyl-4-methylpyrimidine.

A mixture of the amidine hydrochloride and ethoxymethylene compound in sodium ethoxide solution was gently boiled for an hour. The deep orange colour which developed at first gradually faded and the condensation product separated on cooling in crystals that were filtered, washed and repeatedly crystallised from dilute acetone with water, with the aid of animal charcoal. Even after three such purifications the substance melted slowly between 113°-15°C and it could not be further purified.

(Found: N=11.63. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2$, requires N=11.57 per cent.)

Condensation with Naphthamidine: Formation of 5-Acetyl-2-β-naphthyl-4-methylpyrimidine.

The reaction was exactly analogous to that described above the condensation being completed by boiling for an hour. A very poor yield of the product was obtained. On crystallisation from acetone solution with addition of animal charcoal it melted at 151-53°C.

(Found: N=10.88. $C_{17}H_{14}O_1N_2$, requires N=10.70 per cent.)

(d) *Pyrimidine from Ethyl Ethoxymethylenemalonate.*

Condensation with Guanidine: Formation of Ethyl 4-keto-2-amido-1:4-dihydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

The guanidine carbonate was added to the alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide, quickly followed by the

ethyl ethoxy-methylene-malonate and the mixture was constantly stirred. A solid began to separate and within a little over a quarter of an hour the whole set to a hard mass. Instead of heating on the water-bath, it was left undisturbed overnight when it was observed that the hard mass slackened to a loose white deposit. The alcohol was evaporated. The aqueous solution of the residue was just acidified and the precipitate filtered and washed. It hardly dissolved in the neutral solvents. Although fairly soluble in glacial acetic acid, it could not be obtained in any well defined crystalline form but in minute grains melting at 285°C .

(Found : $\text{N} = 23.14$. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires $\text{N} = 22.95$ per cent.)

The corresponding acid from the ethyl ester was obtained by hydrolysing the latter with alcoholic potash for five hours. The alcohol was evaporated, residue dissolved in water, filtered and made just acid with dilute mineral acid when white granular crystals were obtained. It did not dissolve in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform, etc., and so it was purified by precipitation from alkaline solution. It melted with decomposition at 238°C .

(Found : $\text{N} = 27.02$. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{N}_3$ requires $\text{N} = 27.09$ per cent.)

Isolation of the Intermediate Product in the Condensation of Guanidine with Ethyl Ethoxymethylenemalonate.

Formation of $\text{NH}_2\text{C}(\text{NH}_2) : \text{N} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}(\text{COOEt}) : \text{CHOEt}$. Ethyl ester of Ethoxy-methylene malon-guanidic acid.

To investigate what the solid first separates in the above condensation, the mixture was not allowed to stand overnight but the process of condensation interrupted, by filtering it after an hour, washing the ppt. with alcohol and decomposing the sodium compound with glacial

acetic acid. Dilute hydrochloric acid could not be used here since the whole dissolved in it owing no doubt to the pronounced basic nature of the liberated product. When crystallized from glacial acetic acid it was obtained in grains that melted at 295°C. with a shrinking far below this temperature. The combustion value agrees with the supposition that guanidine and ethoxymethylene compound have combined in it to an open chain derivative with the elimination of only one molecule of alcohol.

(Found: N=18.73. $C_8H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N=18.33.)

Transformation of the Intermediate Compound to $(NH_2)_2C : N.COCH_2.COOH$, Malon-guanidic acid.

The hydrolysis of the ethyl ester and removal of the hydroxymethylene group was effected by dissolving it in 50% hydrochloric acid and heating under reflux. Immediately on boiling a granular product separated and within five minutes the quantity was considerable. After continuing the hydrolysis for an hour, it was filtered and washed. It melts at 254°C with decomposition.

(Found: N=28.68. $C_4H_7O_3N_3$ requires N=28.96 per cent.)

Condensation with Anisamidine. Formation of Ethyl 4-keto-2-anisyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

The mixture of ethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate, anisamidine and sodium dissolved in alcohol was boiled on the water-bath for an hour, the alcohol evaporated and the aqueous solution acidified as usual. The condensation product was collected, washed and crystallized from a large excess of boiling alcohol. It melts at 222°-24°C.

(Found: N=10.35. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N=10.20 per cent.)

The hydrolysis of the above ethyl ester gave an acid which was found to be the same as was obtained by hydrolysing the cyanopyrimidone produced by condensing guanidine with ethyl ethoxymethylenecyanacetate.

Condensation with β -Naphthamidine: Formation of Ethyl-4-keto-2-naphthyl-1,4-dihydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate.

The reaction was brought about exactly according to the above procedure. The product was repeatedly crystallised from glacial acetic acid and yet the slight greenish-yellow tinge and its shrinking below the melting point could not be got rid of. It melted at 213-15°C.

The corresponding acid, obtained by digesting the above product with alcoholic potash for 5 hours, was found identical with the one derived from the cyano compound by boiling the latter with sulphuric acid.

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